

MASTS POLICY BRIEF

Protecting Scotland's Deep Sea in a Changing Climate

Interactive
Story Map

Rosemary Bank Seamount approximately 800 m

Deep In The Sea

Most of the United Kingdom's deep sea (deeper than 200 m) is in Scottish waters. Scotland's deep sea, here highlighted in blue, is around four times bigger than Scotland itself. However, this does not reflect the large volume of Scotland's deep sea, which has an average depth of approximately 1,555 m.

Its deep sea hosts a diverse range of habitats, such as submarine ridges, banks, sea mounts, coral and sponge reefs, expansive soft sediments and sand waves. Biodiversity in these habitats is extremely high but their ecosystems are threatened by human-induced climate change, pollution, and the extraction of fish and other resources.

Key Messages

Deep-sea environments, in contrast to coastal ecosystems, are generally less adaptive to environmental changes and its species and habitats are therefore **more sensitive** to climate change impacts.

The **ocean has absorbed** most of the additional heat and about a quarter of the additional atmospheric carbon dioxide from human activities. Even though this has helped keep the planet **cooler** than it would otherwise be, this has also caused **deep-sea ecosystems** to increase in temperature and acidity, lose oxygen, and have less food available.

These changes to deep-sea ecosystems will:

- reduce the capacity of deep-sea sediments to store carbon and recycle nutrients;
- impact coral reef structure and complexity, reducing associated biodiversity and functions;
- impact deep-sea sponges risking, for example, a loss of natural pharmaceuticals; and
- impact fishing activities.

The Challenge

Climate-forced changes pose a very significant risk to the health and biodiversity of Scotland's deep-sea environments, impacting key deep-sea ecosystems, habitats and services. Changes in ecosystem services may be detrimental to the UK economy, and exacerbate the future impacts of climate change.

Existing Protective Measures

Scotland is already taking steps to protect its deep-sea environment:

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs):

MPAs safeguard various species, including cold-water coral reefs and deep-sea sponge aggregations. They protect deep-sea ecosystems against harmful activities, strengthening their capacity for recovery and resilience in the face of climate impacts. Scotland has Europe's largest MPA; West of Scotland MPA¹, designated specifically to protect its deep-sea habitats and species, such as deep-sea sharks.

Priority Marine Features (PMFs):

PMFs (species and habitats of conservation importance) are protected within the National Marine Plan, further safeguarding deep-sea features from the impact of development and licensed activities.

Fisheries management:

The deep sea in Scotland is protected by several existing measures, including seasonal closures on particular species such as blue ling, prohibitions on bottom-contact fishing gear below 800 m in Scottish waters, and fishing restrictions below 200 m designed to protect Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and species such as deep-sea shark species.

¹ jncc.gov.uk/our-work/west-of-scotland-mpa

Orange Roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*)

Recommendations

By taking decisive action to address climate change, strengthen existing protections, and fill critical knowledge gaps, Scotland can ensure the long-term health and resilience of its unique and valuable deep-sea ecosystems. The following actions are recommended:

- 1. Assess the resilience of the existing Marine Protected Area (MPA) network to climate change.** Identify climate change refugia and predict shifts in ecological connectivity, informing adaptive management strategies and the development of strategic approaches to ensure MPAs effectively protect deep-sea features under current and future conditions.
- 2. Reduce existing human pressures to support resilience and recovery.** This will increase the opportunities for resilience of species and habitats to the impacts of climate change, improving their ability to adapt and survive. This protects the many benefits that Scottish people receive from the deep sea.
- 3. Address knowledge gaps.** Impacts of climate-induced environmental change at species, habitat and ecosystem level, that are in addition to the impacts of fishing and pollutants, require continued investigation. This should include pelagic ecosystems, vulnerable and important species (e.g. sponges, corals, fish), deep-sea sediments and the carbon sink.
- 4. Strongly advocate for global reductions in greenhouse gas emissions.**

Coral structures extending from a deep-sea reef wall

Find Out More

This publication was commissioned by the Marine Alliance for Science and Technology for Scotland (MASTS) and produced by the MASTS Working Group "Understanding Climate Change Impacts around Scottish Deep Seas".

The Working Group also created a more in-depth Story Map - an interactive and virtual tool, highlighting main climate change drivers and case studies as well as predictions of future scenarios and recommendations for policymakers and other stakeholders involved.

To explore the Story Map
please visit
<https://bit.ly/ScottishDeepSeas>
or scan the QR Code below:

Deep-sea scene

Policy Brief Authorship:

Johanne Vad¹, Kelly James², Kristina K. Beck¹, Eirian Kettle³, Dominique Anderson⁴, Daniëlle de Jonge³, Teresa Fernandes⁴, Andrew Sweetman⁵, Lucy Goodwin⁶ and Colin Moffat⁷.

1 University of Edinburgh, 2 NatureScot, 3 JNCC, 4 Heriot-Watt University, 5 SAMS, 6 University of Liverpool, 7 Robert Gordon University

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of EDINBURGH

About MASTS: Formed in 2009, the Marine Alliance for Science and Technology for Scotland is a consortium of 19 organisations engaged in marine science and represents the majority of Scotland's marine research capacity. MASTS Research Forums and Working Groups form the major scientific driving force of the MASTS community, serving as platforms of expertise, networking and knowledge exchange. Contact masts@st-andrews.ac.uk for more info.

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